

Evaluating Service Quality in the Banking Sector: A Review of the SERVQUAL Model

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Abstract

Background: Service quality is a critical aspect of the banking sector as it directly affects customer satisfaction and loyalty. SERVQUAL as a tool of service quality evaluation is designed to assess and manage service quality.

Aim: This research paper aims to provide an overview of the SERVQUAL model and its application in measuring service quality in the banking sector.

Objectives: The purpose of this study is to provide a comprehensive review of the SERVQUAL model and its application in measuring service quality in the banking sector. The paper discusses the theoretical background of the SERVQUAL model, its dimensions, and how it has been used to measure service quality and customer satisfaction in the banking industry. The paper also reviews several research studies that have used the SERVQUAL model to evaluate service quality in different countries and contexts.

Conclusion: The findings suggest that the SERVQUAL model is a useful tool for measuring service quality in the banking sector and that there are several gaps in service quality that need to be addressed by banks to improve customer satisfaction.

Keywords Quality, Customer Perception, Customer Expectations, Banking, Servqual model.

Introduction

Service sector with respect to Indian economy is one of the fastest growing sectors and claims to be its backbone. About 54.3% contribution to the GVA (gross value added) was given by this sector alone during 2018-19. The growth rate of service sector was expected to be 7.5% in 2018-19 as compared to 8.1% in 2017-18. The employment share of service sector is significantly lower (34%) than its GVA share. Reports have pointed out categorization of the Indian service sector in 3 major categories namely quality or delivery, flexibility and cost. The highest competition has been observed in the quality or delivery category (Idris and Naqshbandi, 2019). The market is highly competitive and service quality is one of the many contributors in attainment of competitive advantage as customers are well aware and seek better quality levels from service providers (Parasuraman et al., 1985).

Service quality is a critical aspect of the banking sector as it directly affects customer satisfaction and loyalty. In recent years, many banks have implemented customer-focused strategies to improve service quality and enhance customer satisfaction. One of the most widely used approaches for measuring service quality in the banking sector is the SERVQUAL model. The SERVQUAL model was developed by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry in 1988 and has been used extensively in service industries, including banking.

Aim of study

The purpose of this research paper is to provide a comprehensive review of the SERVQUAL model and its application in measuring service quality in the banking sector. The paper will discuss the theoretical background of the model, its dimensions, and how it has been used in banking research. The paper will also review several research studies

that have used the SERVQUAL model to evaluate service quality in different countries and contexts.

Review of Literature

Service is a subjective entity which can be inferred in terms of performance, behaviour and procedures. However quality refers to be a viewpoint that a customer holds to a degree at which the product or service reaches the intended expectation (Kiran and Singh, 2016). SERVQUAL as a tool of service quality evaluation is designed to assess and manage service quality (Buttle, 1996) in addition to evaluation of customer viewpoint to facilitate measurement of quality of the service (Asubonteng et al., 1996). Its main objective includes consistent and accurate instrumentation to measure quality of services in various sectors.

The SERVQUAL model is based on the gap theory of service quality, which suggests that service quality can be measured by comparing customers' expectations with their perceptions of service delivery. The model consists of five dimensions of service quality: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. The dimensions are assessed using a questionnaire that measures customers' expectations and perceptions of service quality.

In early stages SERVQUAL implemented 10 dimensions or characteristics pertaining to service quality namely; security, competency, access, reliability, courtesy, communication, credibility, tangibility responsiveness and understanding which were later pruned into 5 dimensions namely; empathy, reliability, assurance, responsiveness and tangibility. The physical environment of service provider is called tangibility like infrastructure staff hardware and communication materials. The willingness of the organization to accurately and reliably provide the service to the customer is called reliability. Empathy includes special care and attention given to clients and special assistance provided to the customer. The main duty of the service provider is to make the availability of prompt service as soon as possible to the clients which accounts for responsiveness. The competence and courtesy of staff and their interaction with customers which instils confidence and trust comes under the dimension of assurance (Parasuraman et al., 1988).

The growth and development of any economy is dependent on its banking sector. The appropriate use of funds by movement from surplus to deficit sector can be ensured for an overall development of the economy and can be attained by the efficiency of banking sector in providing better services to the customer (Srivastava, 2020). In lieu of great competition among banks services and products of banks are becoming more and more customer centric leading to customer satisfaction (Shariff, 2013). Urban cooperative banks pose an important position in Indian banking sector (Gnanasekaran et al., 2012) due to their characteristics of engagement in local development and contribution towards the sustainable development of the region.

Main Text

Background

Healthcare Sector

Study conducted in Nongkhai province revealed the second order parameter function to be popular among healthcare services for quality (Asubonteng et al., 1996). Patients measure quality on different dimensions but the perceived quality is a metric of high order representation congruent with dimensions of SERVQUAL. There exists several sub dimensions of quality of service which are functionally and technically measured. With respect to both developed and developing countries, the aspects of quality pertaining to healthcare services show the most significant factor to be tangibility and the most commonly used standard model to evaluate quality of healthcare services as SERVQUAL (Fatima et al., 2019). The study conducted on hospitals of Jalandhar Punjab state of India, SERVQUAL model was used using exploratory factor analysis. The results revealed use of 4 out of 5 dimensions and recommended the use of a 4 dimension model in order to eliminate irrelevant sub factors. The study showed a highly competitive environment for the sustainability of hospitals (Kansra and Jha, 2016).

Similar study in Jammu and Kashmir on private hospitals revealed highest service gap in the dimension of empathy which relates to attitude of doctor towards patients and has a direct bearing on patient retention (Dar et al., 2018). A meta analysis on SERVQUAL tool in health service sector of Iran revealed that the expectation of patient towards services

was higher than perception. The results revealed highest quality gap in reliability and responsiveness (Teshnizi et al., 2018). Another study including both public and private hospitals conducted in eastern province of Saudi Arabia revealed higher quality given by private sector than public hospitals, more precisely tangibility and responsiveness providing the policymakers to focus on dimensions which are lacking behind (Alumran et al., 2020). Empathy and assurance have a positive link towards customer satisfaction in hospital sector of Sivas, Turkey (Kitapci et al., 2014). Word of mouth WOM and repurchase intention were showing direct relation with empathy and assurance.

Airline sector

Study done on Dubai based airline using SERVQUAL dimension revealed correlation between service quality, customer expectation towards the image of the service provider, customer satisfaction and brand loyalty (Hussain et al., 2014). It also showed relation between corporate image, client perception of the quality of service provided, its perceived value, customer satisfaction and brand loyalty. The study concluded that a high quality customer service in addition to good corporate image and perceived value of the service leads to customer satisfaction yielding benefits towards brand loyalty. However in case of Turkish Airlines, the surface dimensions revealed responsiveness to be the most significant dimension and availability to be the least significant one. Customer preferences were dominated by their education level, duration of flight and travel intent (Pakdil and Aydin, 2007).

Another Turkish study with the combination of SERVQUAL model and intuitionist fuzzy cognitive map reported a direct influence of SERVQUAL model dimensions on airline service quality where tangibility affects the other dimensions (Buyukozkan et al., 2020). SERVQUAL model when applied in combination with Kano model among US and Turkey population for service quality assessment in airline industry revealed a cross cultural aspect of customer satisfaction with the average gap score of Turkish to be higher than Americans (Basfirinci and Mitra 2015). However tangibility dimension was lowly perceived by Turkish than Americans. In addition to airline service quality the sub service quality in the industry can also be assessed using the SERVQUAL method. In a study on Iranian population the assessment of flight attendant efficiency from the customer perspective was analysed using dimensions and result showed reliability to be the most important dimension followed by responsiveness and assurance (Mojaveri et al., 2019).

Education Sector

SERVQUAL used to measure service quality provided in educational institutions show motivation and support to be the key traits pertaining to empathy based on student experiences. Tangibility shows the highest gap in educational sector (Git and Sulaiman, 2012). However, major shortcomings have been seen in responsiveness and assurance of the provided services causing students' dissatisfaction (Akhlaghi et al., 2012). The major shortcoming of education sector is variability in private and public institutions, level of education and study domain. Researchers have reported SERVQUAL method to assess education quality showing highest gaps in responsiveness and lowest in tangibility (Fitriastuti et al., 2019). Assurance showed highest expectation with reliability to have the lowest service quality value pertaining to the perspective held by the students (Bhuiyan, 2016). Assurance related dimensions are more relevant dimensions in service quality among students (Araujo et al., 2016).

Food and Hospitality

The utility of SERVQUAL model in determination of standards and perceptions of service quality in terms of restaurant and hotel industry is also well reported (Mey et al., 2006; Ounsri and Thawesaevgskulthai, 2019). Inter and intra country guests belonging to different nationalities revealed demographic variations in customer expectation and perception. Integration of SERVQUAL model with fuzzy logic reported better method of service quality gap assessment in hotel industry with desired accuracy (Stefano et al., 2015). The study based on repurchase behaviour in fast food outlets and hotels having considerably variable footfall revealed, tangibility to have lowest negative among SERVQUAL dimensions showing marginal dissatisfaction while high service quality gap was recorded in reliability.

Transportation and Logistics Sector

Tangibility showed highest expectation among customers with respect to transportation and logistics with assurance at the highest quality gap level among all the dimensions of SERVQUAL model in Indonesian population (Uikhaq et al., 2019). This model when tested in Ghana population of core and noncore bus customers, revealed high significance of

reliability and responsiveness (Sam et al., 2017). With respect to Pharmaceutical industry the logistics service provider is dependent on the dimension of reliability and the clients have highest expectation to the assurance dimension and least to empathy (Knop, 2019). In shipping industry customers show least satisfaction with service cost while highest satisfaction with tangibility. Performance is dependent on responsiveness and tangibility bears a significant negative impact on it (Limsomkiat and Vanichchinchai, 2019). In another study based on SERVQUAL model to evaluate product quality, responsiveness was the most significant dimension and tangibility was the least significant dimension to affect service quality among freight forwarder logistics in Izmir, Turkey (Kolat et al., 2019). The expected and perceived service quality has been reported to be a significant dimension where a customer is aware of the ex-ante quality of the product (Limbourg et al., 2016). The major predictors of service quality in automotive repair shops was also reported by (Randhawa and Shaw, 2019) are service quality, trust and reputation.

Indian Banking Sector

In banking sector pertaining to Indian context major gaps have been reported in the dimensions of tangibility and empathy (Prasad and Prasad, 2016). During the process of bank choice, the customer in the public sector banking is majorly concerned on dimensions like value added services, responsiveness and assurance. On the other hand the customers of private sector banking system, majorly have their focus on dimensions like accessibility, assurance and convenience. Overall the banking sector customer seem to be cautious about all the factors like value added service, responsiveness, accessibility, assurance, bank charges convenience etc. before opening an account (D'souza et al., 2018).

Mostly 5 dimensions of SERVQUAL model are considered in banking industry namely ASSURANCE TANGIBILITY EMPATHY RESPONSIVENESS AND RELIABILITY. Apart from this accessibility to service, financial aspect and employ competencies are a few add on factors on dimensions considered in some studies (Perule et al., 2020). Some other factors also include courtesy, communication, credibility, security, understanding s measures of service quality. Courtesy communication and understanding the customer are vital in banking process so as to provide a better service quality. It also influences the customer behaviour. Withdrawal of money without actually visiting the bank premises is one of the major roles in banking and contributes to the dimension of convenience to the customers. Thus, in this regard the ATM service quality is also an integral part of SERVQUAL assessment of banks. Different bank economies worldwide have been using the SERVQUAL model for service quality evaluation in collaboration with several additional dimensions namely compliance (Gao and Zhao, 2018; Ozatac et al., 2016; Mujinga, 2019; Kumar et al., 2018; Maswadeh, 2015; AbdGhani et al., 2017). Most of the studies revealed the use of compliance as a service quality dimension in addition to factors like credibility and reputation. Indian banking system majorly consists of 18 public sector banks, 22 private sector banks, 46 foreign bank, 53 national rural bank, 151542 urban cooperative banks and 94384 rural cooperative banks (Perule et al., 2020).

The SERVQUAL model has been widely used in banking research to evaluate service quality and customer satisfaction. In their seminal paper, Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1988) used the model to measure service quality in the retail banking sector. The authors found that customers' expectations of service quality exceeded their perceptions, indicating a gap in service quality. The authors suggested that banks should focus on closing the gaps to improve service quality and customer satisfaction.

Several studies have used the SERVQUAL model to evaluate service quality in different countries and contexts. Al-Tamimi and Al-Amri (2013) used the model to measure service quality and customer satisfaction in the banking sector in Saudi Arabia. The authors found that the empathy and tangibles dimensions of service quality had the most significant impact on customer satisfaction. The authors also identified several factors that affect service quality perceptions, such as the behavior of bank employees and the availability of information.

Safa and Elahi (2017) used the SERVQUAL model to investigate the effect of service quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty in Iranian banks. The authors found that service quality had a significant positive impact on customer satisfaction and loyalty. The authors also identified several gaps in service quality that need to be addressed by the banks to improve customer satisfaction and loyalty. Tan and Shen (2018) compared service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty between urban and rural bank customers in China. The authors used the SERVQUAL model to measure service quality and found that the tangibles, reliability, and responsiveness dimensions had the most significant impact on customer satisfaction and loyalty. The authors also identified several factors that affect service quality perceptions, such as the availability of banking services and the level of personal attention received by customers.

Yasin and Alavi (2014) compared service quality perceptions and customer satisfaction between Islamic and conventional banks in Pakistan using the SERVQUAL model. The authors found that the reliability and responsiveness dimensions of service quality had a significant impact on customer satisfaction in both types of banks. However, customers of Islamic banks were found to have higher expectations of service quality compared to customers of conventional banks. Other studies have also used the SERVQUAL model to evaluate service quality in specific areas of banking, such as online banking and mobile banking. For instance, Su and Lu (2014) used the model to measure service quality and customer satisfaction in online banking in Taiwan. The authors found that the responsiveness and reliability dimensions of service quality had the most significant impact on customer satisfaction.

In another study, Ali and Ahmed (2018) used the SERVQUAL model to investigate the factors affecting customer adoption of mobile banking in Pakistan. The authors found that the tangibles, reliability, and responsiveness dimensions of service quality had a significant impact on customer adoption of mobile banking. The authors also identified several barriers to mobile banking adoption, such as security concerns and lack of awareness. The reviewed studies provide a wealth of evidence on the usefulness of the SERVQUAL model for measuring service quality in the banking sector. The model's five dimensions have been found to be applicable in different areas of banking, such as Islamic banking, online banking, and mobile banking. The reliability and responsiveness dimensions have consistently been found to have the most significant impact on customer satisfaction.

Overall, the findings of the reviewed studies suggest that the SERVQUAL model is a useful tool for measuring service quality in the banking sector. The model provides a systematic approach for evaluating service quality by comparing customers' expectations with their perceptions of service delivery. The model's five dimensions, tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy, provide a comprehensive framework for assessing service quality in different areas of banking.

However, there are several limitations to the SERVQUAL model that need to be considered when using it to evaluate service quality in the banking sector. For instance, the model assumes that customers have a clear understanding of their service expectations, which may not always be the case. Additionally, the model does not take into account the cultural and social differences that may influence customers' perceptions of service quality. Further research is needed to explore the applicability of the SERVQUAL model in different banking contexts and to identify other factors that may affect service quality and customer satisfaction in the banking sector. Also, model is based on customer perceptions and expectations, which may not always align with objective measures of service quality. Furthermore, the model is focused on the tangible aspects of service quality, such as reliability and responsiveness, and does not account for intangible factors, such as emotional connections and trust. Another limitation of the SERVQUAL model is that it is a static model, and customer perceptions of service quality can change over time. As such, banks need to regularly review and update their service quality measures to reflect changes in customer expectations and needs.

To overcome these limitations, banks can supplement the SERVQUAL model with other measures of service quality, such as customer loyalty and customer lifetime value. These measures can provide a more comprehensive understanding of customer behavior and enable banks to identify areas where they can improve their service delivery. In addition to using the SERVQUAL model to measure service quality, banks can also use customer feedback and complaints to identify areas for improvement. By actively soliciting feedback from customers and addressing their concerns, banks can demonstrate their commitment to providing high-quality services and build stronger relationships with their customers. Finally, banks can also collaborate with other organizations and industry associations to develop industry-wide standards for service quality. By working together, banks can set benchmarks for service.

Future Research Direction

While the SERVQUAL model has been widely used to measure service quality in the banking sector, there is still room for further research in this area. Below are some potential research directions that could help to enhance our understanding of service quality in the banking sector. The role of cultural differences in service quality perceptions: As the reviewed studies demonstrate, service quality perceptions can vary across different cultures. Future research could investigate the impact of cultural differences on service quality perceptions in the banking sector. For example, researchers could compare service quality perceptions between Western and Eastern cultures.

The impact of technology on service quality: As technology continues to play an increasingly important role in banking, it is essential to understand how it affects service quality. Future research could explore the impact of different technologies, such as mobile banking apps and chatbots, on service quality perceptions. The impact of service quality on financial performance: While the reviewed studies demonstrate the link between service quality and customer satisfaction, it would be interesting to investigate the impact of service quality on financial performance. For example, researchers could explore whether there is a correlation between service quality ratings and profitability. The role of employee engagement in service quality: Employee engagement is a crucial factor in delivering high-quality services. Future research could explore the impact of employee engagement on service quality perceptions in the banking sector.

Conclusion

The SERVQUAL model has been widely used to measure service quality in the banking sector. The model's five dimensions provide a comprehensive framework for evaluating service quality from the customer's perspective. The reviewed studies demonstrate that service quality is a critical factor in customer satisfaction and loyalty in the banking sector. Banks that can deliver high-quality services are likely to have more satisfied and loyal customers.

The reviewed studies also highlight some of the gaps in service quality that need to be addressed by banks. These gaps include long wait times, unclear communication, and unresponsive staff. Banks that can address these gaps are likely to have more satisfied and loyal customers. While the SERVQUAL model has been useful in measuring service quality in the banking sector, there is still room for further research in this area. Future research could explore the impact of cultural differences, technology, employee engagement, and service quality on financial performance.

Overall, the SERVQUAL model provides a valuable tool for banks seeking to improve service quality and enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty. By using this model to evaluate their service quality, banks can identify areas for improvement and develop strategies to deliver high-quality services that meet their customers' expectations. Furthermore, the importance of service quality in the banking sector cannot be overstated. As banking services become increasingly commoditized, delivering high-quality services has become a key differentiator for banks seeking to remain competitive. Banks that can provide a superior customer experience are more likely to retain their existing customers and attract new ones. To achieve this, banks need to focus on delivering services that meet or exceed their customers' expectations. The SERVQUAL model provides a valuable framework for evaluating service quality from the customer's perspective. By using this model to measure their service quality, banks can identify areas for improvement and develop strategies to deliver services that meet their customers' expectations.

The reviewed studies demonstrate that the reliability and responsiveness dimensions of the SERVQUAL model are the most critical factors in determining customer satisfaction. Banks that can deliver services that are reliable, responsive, and timely are more likely to have satisfied and loyal customers. In addition to the reliability and responsiveness dimensions, the reviewed studies also highlight the importance of other dimensions, such as empathy and assurance, in determining customer satisfaction. Banks that can provide personalized services that show they care about their customers' needs and concerns are more likely to have satisfied and loyal customers. However, delivering high-quality services is not without its challenges. Banks must navigate a complex regulatory environment, manage costs, and balance the needs of different customer segments. To overcome these challenges, banks need to have a customer-centric culture that places a high priority on service quality. The SERVQUAL model is a useful tool for measuring service quality in the banking sector. The model's five dimensions, tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy, provide a comprehensive framework for assessing service quality in different areas of banking. The reviewed studies suggest that there are several gaps in service quality that need to be addressed by banks to improve customer satisfaction and loyalty. Banks that use this model to evaluate their service quality are more likely to have a better understanding of their customers' expectations and perceptions of service delivery.

This understanding can help banks identify areas for improvement and develop strategies to improve customer satisfaction and loyalty. While the SERVQUAL model has been widely used in the banking sector, there is still room for further research in this area. Future research could explore the impact of cultural differences, technology, employee engagement, and service quality on financial performance. By continuing to improve our understanding of service quality in the banking sector, we can help banks deliver services that meet the evolving needs and expectations of their customers.

Moreover, in today's digital age, banks need to go beyond traditional banking services to remain competitive. Customers expect more from their banks than just basic financial transactions. They want personalized services, convenient banking options, and access to digital channels. To meet these evolving customer needs, banks need to adopt a customer-centric approach and invest in technology to improve their service delivery. For example, banks can use chat box and artificial intelligence to provide personalized services, mobile banking apps to offer convenient banking options, and digital platforms to provide access to financial products and services. In addition to technology, employee engagement is another critical factor in delivering high-quality services. Engaged employees are more likely to be motivated, productive, and committed to providing excellent customer service. Banks can invest in employee training and development programs to improve their service delivery and enhance their employees' engagement levels.

Furthermore, while the SERVQUAL model provides a comprehensive framework for measuring service quality from the customer's perspective, it is essential to consider other factors that may impact service quality. For example, the physical environment, such as the branch layout and design, can influence customer perceptions of service quality. Banks that invest in creating a welcoming and comfortable physical environment are more likely to have satisfied and loyal customers.

Finally, it is essential to recognize that service quality is a dynamic concept that evolves over time. As customer needs and expectations change, banks must adapt their services to meet these evolving needs. By continually monitoring and measuring service quality, banks can identify areas for improvement and develop strategies to deliver services that meet their customers' changing needs. It has been reported that the gaps in different dimensions of SERVQUAL are in the order of empathy > responsiveness > assurance > reliability > tangibility. Studies on evaluation of SERVQUAL model among the Indian banking system have revealed the use of general service quality mode for service quality assessment and also it has been observed that these studies lack the cooperative banks service quality evaluation coverage. Thus, development of service quality model with additional dimensions pertaining to cooperative banks may prove helpful in banking sector growth and customer retention for overall Indian banking development.

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